

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

ASSOCIATION OF ALANINE AMINOTRANSFERASES (ALT) LEVELS WITH RISK FACTORS INVOLVED IN THE SPREAD OF HCV IN PATIENTS OF DISTRICT RAWALPINDI, PAKISTAN

Haris Rasool¹, Hafiza Mamoona Zulfiqar¹, Asma Arshad²

¹Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad-Pakistan

²Quaid e Azam Medical College Bahawalpur-Pakistan

Article Received: May 2020

Accepted: June 2020

Published: July 2020

Abstract:

Introduction: Hepatitis C virus (HCV) is one of the most renowned viruses of family Flaviviridae, and is the causal agent for hepatitis C. HCV causes liver damage, functional impairment, liver shrinkage and hepatocellular carcinoma.

Aim: Present research was designed to find out the relationship of ALT (Alanine Aminotransferase) levels with the most recently known risk factors.

Study design: A cross-sectional study. Place and duration of the study: Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences and Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi for one year duration from March 2019 to December 2019.

Methods: Data was taken from 1200 patients visiting the out patients departments of the two main hospitals of Rawalpindi. Study participants were 14% males and 86% females, with 93% chronicity cases, ages of majority ranged between 40-49 years, non-addicts and from low socioeconomic status, representatives of all walks of life. A questionnaire was designed on the life habits, risk factors and demographics of the patients

Results: There was a significant co-relation between ALT levels and reported risk factors at 90% CI ($p < 0.07$). While the correlation between ALT levels and gender was non-significant at 90% CI ($p < 0.190$). A general trend of increasing ALT levels above the age of 40 was observed.

Conclusion: Regression analysis proved that blood transfusions, dental procedures and injections were the prominent risk factors involved in the spread of disease.

Key Words: Hepatitis C, Liver Functioning Test, Alanineamino Transfeases, Chronic HCV, Dental Procedures, Risk Factors

Corresponding author:

Haris Rasool,

Faisalabad Medical University,

Faisalabad-Pakistan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Haris Rasool et al, Association Of Alanine Aminotransferases (Alt) Levels With Risk Factors Involved In The Spread Of HCV In Patients Of District Rawalpindi, Pakistan., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(07).

INTRODUCTION:

One of the most important cytosolic Enzymes is Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and liver cell injury results in the leakage of ALT into the circulation. In the history of Hepatic diseases diagnosis and therapy (particularly hepatitis), the role of serum ALT levels have played a significant role (1,2). Steadily documented abnormal values of ALT were once considered standard, at the time when hepatitis C was termed as non-A non-B hepatitis (3). With the advancement in technology and use of molecular based techniques world over, it was found that HCV viremia remains latent or asymptomatic in 25%-30% of the documented chronic cases with persistently normal ALT (40 IU/L) levels (PNAL) (4,5,6).

No test uniformly predicts which individuals will have persistent infection, develop cirrhosis, or respond to therapy, although viral load, HCV genotype, liver histology, and serum transaminases have been studied (7,8,9). Although considerable literature exists on the subset of HCV patients with normal ALT, little is known of the role of ALT level in different known modes of spread involved in HCV as inoculum size varies from different sources as well as the aggression of virus depends on its genotype.

Serum ALT measurements are economical, easily performed, readily available and still globally used in the managing HCV infection. Till 1997, the recommendations of NIH Consensus Panel for HCV treatment were that, individuals with normal ALT levels should not receive interferon therapy for HCV infection (8). In addition, the result of a single ALT determination radically affected the frequency with which liver biopsies were performed in the past (10,11). The objectives of the study were to find the association between risk factors involved in raised ALT levels in HCV positive index cases and to find the association of gender and ALT levels in studied cohort.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In order to find the possible existing relationship between modes of HCV spread and levels of ALT a study was designed by taking the data on the modes of disease accusation and its association with the ALT levels. Data was taken from 1200 patients

visiting the out patients departments of the two main hospitalsof rawalpindi. The study was reviewed and approved by the review boards and ethical committee of the both institutes. All the patients were the representatives of the low socioeconomic status and were from Gujar Khan. A questionnaire was designed on the life habits, risk factors and demographics of the patients. Consents were taken from all the patients before collection of blood and data.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients positive for HCV by ELISA and patients between the ages 12-65.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients co-infected with HBV and HIV, Patients aged less than 12 and more than 65 years, Female patients with pregnancy, Patients on interferon treatment and patients with cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma.

5ml of the blood was taken in purple top vaccutainers provided with K3-EDTA. Plasma was extracted from the blood and was stored at -80°C till further analysis. ALT levels were taken in triplicate and their average was calculated. ALT was correlated with risk factors and genders using statistical software (minitab 11, ordinal regression, binary logit regression and co-relation).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In this study comparison was made between two study groups i.e with normal and elevated ALT levels (Table 1 & 2). It is observed that majority of the female cases were asymptomatic and with normal PNALs ($P < .001$), and have a lower incidence of risk factors for HCV transmission ($P < .01$). All patients with normal ALT had significant histological liver damage. Patients with normal ALT levels had similar serum HCV-RNA titers than subjects with raised ALT. Neither HCV genotype distribution nor viral load correlated with the severity of liver damage. Majority of the reported cases were females and the most pronounced risk factors were unknown, injections and dental procedures. Most of the ALT levels resided between 42-84 U/L (37%) in the patients of age group 30-50 years.

Table 1: Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) above the upper limit of normal in the sera of patients with chronic HCV carriers.

Total number of patients 1073		
Levels of ALT U/L	Number of cases	Percentages
<42	320	30%
42-84	403	37%
85-126	168	16%
>126	182	17%

Table 2: Ordinal logistic regression analysis for risk factors and raised ALT levels.

Risk Factors	Odd Ratios	CI	P Values	Risk Factors	Odd Ratios	CI	P Values
1	1	1	0.000***	20	1	1	0.000***
2	1	1	0.000***	21	1	1	0.000***
3	1	1	0.000***	22	1	1	0.000***
4	1	1	0.000***	23	1	1	0.000***
5	1	1	0.007	24	1	1	0.000***
6	1	1	0.049	25	1	1	0.000***
7	1	1	0.452	26	1	1	0.000***
8	1	1	0.768	27	1	1	0.000***
9	1	1	0.716	28	1	1	0.000***
10	1	1	0.443	29	1	1	0.000***
11	1	1	0.262	30	1	1	0.000***
12	1	1	0.203	31	1	1	0.000***
13	1	1	0.005	32	1	1	0.000***
14	1	1	0.000***	33	1	1	0.000***
15	1	1	0.000***	34	1	1	0.000***
16	1	1	0.000***	35	1	1	0.000***
17	1	1	0.000***	36	1	1	0.000***
18	1	1	0.000***	37	1	1	0.000***
19	1	1	0.000***	38	1	1	0.000***

(1) Unknown, (2) Injection, (3) Surgery, (4) Dental procedures, (5) Sexual exposure, (6) Vertical transmission, (7) Barber shears, (8) Accidental blood exposure, (9) Blood transfusion, (10) Tattoos, (11) Child birth, (12) Needle prick, surgery, (13) Needle prick, child birth, (14) Sexual exposure, surgery, (15) Sexual exposure, child birth, (16) Surgery, blood transfusion, (17) Surgery, dental procedures, (18) Surgery, barber shears, (19) Surgery, shared razors & tooth brushes, (20) Therapeutic injection, (21) Child birth, (22) Blood transfusion, dental procedures, (23) Blood transfusion, therapeutic injection, (24) Blood transfusion, child birth, (25) Dental procedures, therapeutic injections, (26) Dental procedures, tattoos, (27) Dental procedures, barber shears, (28) Dental procedures, shared razors & tooth brushes, (29) Dental procedures, child birth, (30) Barber shears, shared razors, (31) Barber shears, tattoos, (32) Barber shears, documented blood exposure, (33) Injection, child birth, (34) Blood transfusion, sexual exposure, (35) Injection, sexual exposure, (36) Dental, sexual exposure, (37) Injection, vertical transmission, (38) Injections, sexual exposures

Raised ALT levels were generally recorded in specifically unknown, injections, surgery, dental procedures and also in the combination of these risk factors.

There was a significant association of almost all risk factors with ALT level p -Value < 0.01 whereas needle pricks, barber shears, tatoos and child birth (minor risk factors) are an exception. According to binary logistic regression analysis, the association of raised ALT level with gender was non-significant (p -value 1).

Fig 1. (a) Probability plot for ages-ALT level **(b)** Probability plot for ages-ALT level

In a study conducted by (12) with dialysis patients, it was observed that detectable HCV RNA in serum was a well-built autonomous predictor of raised ALT values; the bond between serum ALT values and anti-HCV antibody was entirely linked to the association between raised ALT values and HCV viraemia. A higher hepatic enzyme level was found in HCV RNA positive patients as compared to dialysis patients with no detectable HCV RNA. According to Fabrizi there was no apparent association between HCV genotypes and ALT activity (12). A study suggested that consistently high ALT levels were strongly associated with liver cell damage (13).

CONCLUSION:

There was a significant co-relation between ALT levels and reported risk factors at 90% CI ($p < 0.07$). While the correlation between ALT levels and gender was non-significant at 90% CI ($p < 0.190$). A general trend of increasing ALT levels above the age of 40 was observed. Regression analysis proved that blood transfusions, dental procedures and injections were the prominent risk

factors involved in the spread of disease. There was a significant association of almost all risk factors with ALT level p -Value < 0.01 whereas needle pricks, barber shears, tatoos and child birth (minor risk factors) are an exception. According to binary logistic regression analysis, the association of raised ALT level with gender was non-significant (p -value 1).

REFERENCE:

1. Haber MM, West AB, Haber AD, Reuben A. Relationship of aminotranferases to liver histological status in chronic hepatitis C. *Am J Gastroenterol.* 1995;90:1250-7.
2. Healey CJ, Chapman RW, Fleming KA. Liver histology in hepatitis C infection: A comparison between patients with persistently normal or abnormal transaminases. *Gut.* 1995;37:274-8.
3. Dienstag JL, Alter HJ. Non-A, non-B hepatitis: evolving epidemiologic and clinical perspective. *Semin Liver Dis* 1986;6:67-81.
4. Di Bisceglie AM, Goodman ZD, Ishak KG, Hoofnagle JH, Melpolder JJ, Alter HJ. Long-

- term clinical and histopathological follow-up of chronic posttransfusion hepatitis. *HEPATOLOGY* 1991;14:969-974.
5. Tassopoulos NC. Treatment of patients with chronic hepatitis C and normal ALT levels. *J Hepatol* 1999;31(Suppl 1):193-196.
 6. Marcellin P, Levy S, Erlinger S. Therapy of hepatitis C: patients with normal aminotransferase levels. *HEPATOLOGY* 1997;26:133S-136S.
 7. Davis GL, Lau JYN. Factors predictive of a beneficial response to therapy of hepatitis C. *HEPATOLOGY* 1997;26:122S-127S.
 8. Hoofnagle JH. Hepatitis C: the clinical spectrum of disease. *HEPATOLOGY*. 1997;26:15S-20S.
 9. Seeff LB. Natural history of hepatitis C. *HEPATOLOGY* 1997;26:21S-28S.
 10. Everhart JE, Stolar M, Hoofnagle JH. Management of hepatitis C: a national survey of gastroenterologists and hepatologists. *HEPATOLOGY*. 1997;26:78S-82S.
 11. Thomas VI, Rudra R, Jacquie A, Leislle G, Kenrad EN, David V and David LT. (1999). A Prospective, Community-Based Evaluation of Liver Enzymes in Individuals With Hepatitis C After Drug Use. *Hepatology*. 29(2):590-596.
 12. Fabrizi F, G. Lunghi, S. Andrulli, B. Pagliari, S. Mangano, P. Faranna, A. Pagano and F. Locatelli (1997). Influence of hepatitis C virus (HCV) viraemia upon serum aminotransferase activity in chronic dialysis patients. *Nephrology Dialysis Transplantation*. *Nephrol Dial Transplant*. 12: 1394-1398.
 13. Tarao, K., Y. Rino., Ohkawa S, Shimizu A, Tamai S, Miyakawa K, Aoki H, Imada T, Shindo K, Okamoto N and Totsuka S (1998). Association between high serum alanine aminotransferase levels and more rapid development and higher rate of incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma in patients with hepatitis C virus-associated cirrhosis. *Cancer*. 86(4):589-595.